

NPAR TESTS

/MANN-WHITNEY = SmlArena BY Group (1.00,2.00)

Ranks

	N	Me Ra	Sín Ra
Sml Gr 5	18		590
Ref 5	00	510	
Tb 20			

Test Statistics

	Ma U	W	Z	Apn Sig 2-
Sml	310	510	-.57	.570

NPAR TESTS

/MANN-WHITNEY = MedArena BY Group (1.00,2.00)

Ranks

	N	Me Ra	Sín Ra
Med Gr 5	40		700
Ref 5	933	400	
Tb 20			

Test Statistics

	Ma U	W	Z	Apn Sig 2-
Med	200	400	-.153	.27

NPAR TESTS

/MANN-WHITNEY = LrgArena BY Group (1.00,2.00)

Ranks

	N	Me Ra	Sín Ra
Lrg Gr 5	218		610
Ref 5	973	460	
Tb 20			

Test Statistics

	Ma U	W	Z	Apn Sig 2-
Lrg	260	460	-.10	.35